

**DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF IoT-BASED
LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**

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DECLARATION

This project work is entirely original, approved by my supervisor, and completed by myself. Where collaboration with other persons or information developed by other researchers is utilized, the parties and/or materials are acknowledged in the acknowledgment or clearly described with references, where necessary.

This work is being submitted as part of the Electronic and Computer Engineering Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.) degree requirements.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the project entitled “**Design and Construction of IoT-Based Library Management System**” has been submitted to the Department of Electronic and Computer Engineering, Lagos State University, Lagos, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Science in Electronic and Computer Engineering.

.....
DR. M.A. ADEDOYIN
Project Supervisor

.....
Date

DEDICATION

I dedicate this project to God almighty that alone deserves all the praise for this project; I appreciate His blessings, mercies, and direction in every step taken to achieve all desired results. I also dedicate this project to the beginning teachers, lecturers, tutors from all spheres of life, and my entire family and friends for their support and words of encouragement.

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ABSTRACT

This project combines the basic knowledge of hardware and software to achieve its desired goals. The ever-growing demand for automated solutions has made the Internet of Things (IoT) one of the most important solutions in the field of technology. The smart solution is becoming very useful in our environments today as it keeps changing, the working environment setup transitions from dumb systems to smart solutions have made IoT an important technology as this project is concerned. This project focuses on the design and construction of IoT-based library management system. This will combine both hardware and software resources to achieve its goals.

IoT can be regarded as a digitally connected network of physical devices with a functioning network connection and other interrelated hardware devices such as actuators and sensors to facilitate the internal communication between these components and to ensure external communication among these devices and people around the IoT environment.

Technology-dependent systems are taking over most of the manual management systems in our world today. Technology-driven devices are becoming the best choice of most organizations because of the way they use the Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) hierarchy or pyramid to handle the logical structure of any designed architecture. Most information management-related businesses now use systems with DIKW models to meet the most demanding practical tasks involving information.

Several library management systems have been existing before the introduction of IoT to library activities. Some of the technologies used in previous work involve the barcode system, (Quick Response) QR code, and Near-field communication. Each of these technologies offers different purposes for managing library resources.

The proposed system is based on IoT which will enable both wireless and offline communication between a set of hardware devices and web-based software that runs on a local host. This IoT-based library management enables easy searching and locating of books within the library shelves because indicating Light Emitting Diode (LED) is attached to each row on each shelf to minimize the stress of checking many shelves or many rows before the book of choice can be located. There is also software designed and developed to act as a database-supporting environment which will be available for storing book information such as Title, International Standard Book Number (ISBN), Book Number, Author,

etc. and this software will also have an interactive user interface to enable users to search and locate books.

This IoT-based library management system not only relieves librarians and library users from the stress of searching for the location of books of choice on the shelves but also enables the librarians to keep a record of library resources in a more reliable database rather than the paper file that can be misplaced at any time. The manual method of managing library resources could be very demanding in the terms of cost of keeping book records especially when new books are to be added to the library record. In general, library users are unaware of the particular row in which the book of choice can be found although they might be aware of the shelf of concern based on the labels attached to each shelf. Research shows that most library management systems are being faced with some challenges such as unstable power supply, network problems, etc.

Manual library management operations have been studied to some extent and the need to overcome the problems associated with this manual library management system is the reason behind this proposed IoT-based library management system.

This additional feature allows library users to locate any book of choice within a short time and this, in turn, minimizes the time spent checking through many shelves or rows.

Another improvement this project will add to the previously existing manual library management system is that it involves the use of software that supports a database that is used to store book records in a more efficient manner rather than the usual paper-based method of keeping book records.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The library is an integral part of any educational institution. By definition, a Library can be defined as a special building or room in which a collection of books, journals, manuscripts, periodicals, and printed and non-printed library materials are kept for easy accessibility to meet users' needs [1]. Library as an included facility in an academic environment is simply a way of keeping people around such an environment updated. The library remains a world of books to discover and gain new insights into the unknown. The potential use of the library resources depends on the user's need. Students, lecturers, researchers, and professionals from several other fields continue to consult library resources for distinctive knowledge acquisition. Manual library management operations have been studied to some extent and the need to overcome the problems associated with this manual library management system is the reason behind this proposed Internet of Things (IoT)-based library management system [2]. Technical difficulties encountered during the book searching process in the manual system are one of the reasons behind this project as the design will include an electronics circuit consisting of some components and Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs). The LED in the setup is an indicator to show users the shelf row in which the book they are searching for can be found on the available shelves. This additional feature allows library users to locate any book of choice within a short time and this, in turn, minimizes the time spent checking through many shelves or rows. Although the traditional library management systems still label shelves based on the field in which the books contained are categorized. Searching through rows of a particular shelf one by one could be time-consuming and this makes the newly added feature quite helpful. Another improvement this project will add to the previously existing manual library management system is that it involves the use of software that supports a database that is used to store book records in a more efficient manner rather than the usual paper-based method of keeping book records. This proposed system enables the insertion, deletion, and updating of data into this software. This will enable librarians to keep book records more safely and this will facilitate quick tracking of the library resources. The most intriguing aspect of this project is that the software and the external circuit box communicate wirelessly

as the software runs offline on localhost and hence, it does not depend on the use of the internet before data searching and locating can be done.

IoT-based library management systems will offer a lot of advantages to many organizations in need of it due to their simplicity and accuracy. It is a very effective and efficient facility that will meet the most challenging tasks in any information management-related system.

This project is implemented in such a way that it will imitate a real-life scenario. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) through which a user can input some keywords that are related to the book descriptions for example the International Standard Book Number (ISBN), Book Number, Author's Name, etc. After entering the keyword into the search field, a list of related templates stored in the database will be generated and the user will then select the book that matches the description that matches his request and then finally click on the button named "locate" to see the row in which the searched book is located on the shelf through a blinking LED from the concerned shelf row. Taking Lagos State University, Epe campus as a case study, the library has about "11" well-labeled shelves and each shelf has a few rows in which books are horizontally stacked. But this project will use a single shelf which would be labeled as shelf "A" and it will have five rows. Each row will have an LED connected to it and these LEDs are in turn connected with wires to the electronics circuit box. This circuit box houses some components together with the Wi-enabled microcontroller module called NODEMCU/ESP8266 which enables the circuit to communicate wirelessly with the software that runs the PC.

1.2 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Most libraries in Nigeria still operate manually to keep their daily activities running to meet library users' demands. One of the basic disadvantages of this manual system is that it has no effective means of checking counterfeit records of book details stored on paper.

Detecting counterfeits in the manual system could be quite impossible, if care is not taken similar book numbers can be assigned to different books and this could make it difficult to distinguish between one or more recorded resources in the library.

Hence, the appearance of multiple records that are not well differentiated from each other could result in conflict, especially during manual searching.

Some developed countries have been using electronic library management systems that also enable quick search and locate functionalities for the effective operation of libraries and these added features have greatly improved library activities. The ease with which users can locate library resources on the available shelves has become one of the utmost needs for most libraries.

Information gathered as regards the existing systems has shown that they are error-prone. Possible problems that can be related to the existing systems are highlighted below:

i. Human mistakes:

This is unavoidable when it comes to entering data manually on paper during record keeping. Wrong information could be entered, and duplication of previously existing data is also another problem but there should be a way of distinguishing new entries that have similar data to previous ones. Hence, to avoid data duplication and possible human errors there is a need for a new and reliable method of minimizing those errors.

ii. Time-consuming:

Managing the existing manual library management system is time-consuming in terms of recording new books, correcting pre-recorded book details, and updating records manually because the system will require the librarian to look into several paper files to ensure that the new book recorded belongs to the intended file. Repeated data correction will also mar the look of the paper file and could make it irritating. The time taken to undergo the aforementioned processes is much but for the sake of simplicity, the new system that tries to incorporate an offline website with a good database for data storage will enable all these processes to become easier and data stored will always be in their neat form even after several corrections.

iii. Data Security:

A manual library management system is always unsecured because book records kept on paper files can easily be altered by an authorized person since there is no good security to counter unauthorized access to the paper files. Data loss is also inevitable as paper files can be lost or damaged at any time thereby rendering the library records irretrievable and this could put the librarian in a total mess. Hence, there is a need for centralized data with good rollback and data recovery capabilities.

iv. Ineffective/ Data-Search time:

The manual library management system's use of shelf labels or card catalogs is still not an effective method of enabling the quick location of books in the library. Time used by users for moving from shelf to shelf to locate the book of choice could be very discouraging. Hence, there is a need for every library to incorporate an electronic system that makes the location of the searched book easily visible. To overcome this problem the proposed system has an electronic system that makes searched book locations easily visible.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1.3.1 Aim of the project

This project aims to design and construct an IoT-Based Smart Library Management System that will make both librarians and library users find the library environment more useful in terms of data storage and resource searching and locating in the library. The strategy will allow some library activities to be carried out more easily. As technology continues to grow, the paradigm shift in information management systems is also important.

1.3.2 Objectives of the project

- i. To design and develop software that will enable librarians to store library records in a more secure centralized Database.
- ii. To program a device that controls switches to switch on/off indicators (LEDs) based on signals received from the software.
- iii. To develop an interactive GUI that will enable librarians and library users to search for books and get the book location on the shelf without delay in offline mode.
- iv. To evaluate whether the overall system is reliable after testing and simulation.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

A library as a repository of knowledge is known to consist of hundreds or thousands of books. To keep library books organized, the scope of this study is to design and develop software (offline website) that librarians can use to store and update book information available in the library and also locate books of choice on shelves through some indicating electronics components that have been programmed wirelessly to the designed software. In short, the scope of this project covers information management

and quick searching and locating tools. To also reduce the waiting time of users if many users want to find the location of a book in the library simultaneously, they can do this on different computers in the library as long as every other computer can act as a client on that same network.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROJECT

- (i) A reliable and improved information management system for keeping book records is guaranteed.
- (ii) The proposed system is highly efficient and effective in reducing documentation time and space.
- (iii) It gives librarians a high degree of confidence in the aspect of retrieval of information and data backup during any occurrence of data loss since data is stored in a more secure centralized database.
- (iv) The proposed system is cost-effective as it reduces the expenses of accumulating more paper for data storage. It also reduces the manpower required for library operations to some extent since most processes have now been computerized.
- (v) It offers super-fast delivery of work through the use of electronics, and its incorporated library resource indicating facilities help to completely minimize the time required to locate books on shelves in the library.
- (vi) The proposed system is a great way to eliminate every delay associated with the manual systems of managing library resources.

1.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The implementation covers operations involving the library resources information management and simple “search and locate features” but it does not have features for borrowing books, returning books, and a transaction platform where users can make payments to purchase books which existing systems are used to.

1.7 DEFINITION OF TERMS

- **IoT:** Internet of Things is a term that describes physical objects (things) embedded with sensors and other related software technologies to connect and exchange data over the communication network or internet
- **LED:** Light-emitting diode is a semiconductor device that when an electric current passes through will emit light.
- **PC:** A personal computer is defined as a digital computer designed for use by a single end-user.
- **NodeMCU:** This is an open-source software and hardware environment with the capability of connecting objects and letting data transfer using Wi-Fi protocol.
- **ISBN:** International Standard Book Number: It is a unique identifier usually a 13-digit number assigned to every book.
- **GUI:** A Graphical User Interface is a user interface that allows users to interact with the computer through its visual indicators.

1.8 PROJECT ORGANISATION

The remaining part of this project is organised as follows:

- Introduction (Chapter One): This section discusses the concept library of resource (Book) Locator integrated into an E-library Management System using the knowledge of the IoT to address the problem statement which gives rise to the need for an efficient IoT-based E-Library Management system with Library Resource (Book) Locator, generic structure of IoT-Based E-Library Management System with Library Resource (Book) Locator.
- Literature review (Chapter Two): This section discusses related previously existing work. It also analyses the various components needed for the design and implementation of the project. It is believed that a review of related work would be necessary for outlining problems that have been solved, methods used in solving them, and the solutions achieved. Shortcomings in related work are also accessed in view to make improvements to the proposed design.

- System Analysis and Design Methodology (Chapter Three): This section provides a system overview of the proposed project through a block diagram of the proposed system, a circuit diagram of the system, a data flowchart of the proposed system, and a discussion on the hardware and software design.
- Implementation and Testing (Chapter four): This section provides detailed information on the phases of electrical and software design. The full project, testing, and the problems encountered are discussed here.
- Conclusion and Recommendations (Chapter Five): This section summarises the whole design and construction phases of the project. Recommendations for the future enhancement of the project are also discussed.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

IoT is regarded as a predominant phenomenon in the technology world of today, it continues to have an indispensable influence on all components of human life. The advent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been of great importance to the technological growth of almost every place in the world. As the IoT progresses, it has experienced several positive changes in its size and dimension which have together changed the traditional library system.

IoT has been used extensively in renovating several conventional library systems, and through this, more smart and automated library systems have been realized. IoT smartly describes the connectivity between physical objects and real-time communication technology. Devices behind the use of IoT are sensors, microcontrollers, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, actuators, and many other devices that are capable of sensing events and then communicating the sensed data to a gateway for decision-making [1]-[3].

So many techniques have been used to transform conventional Library Management Systems (LMS) into smart library schemes. Some of the research efforts made to achieve the transformation through the knowledge of ICT and IoT are stated below:

According to [2], the authors presented two possible models for library process prediction such as the T-test and coefficient of determination. Their model was based on the relationship existing between lending and the number of readers and finally used library lending to complete the design and construction of the model library. They were able to use a statistical test to proffer solutions to some drawbacks in the conventional library system. According to their work, the coefficient of determination measures the variability within variable (y). Whereas the T-test statistically compares the means of two groups involved i.e. the lending and the number of readers. Library Management System (LMS) through the use of Visual Basic (VB) was introduced, this is not just a powerful programming language that is

event-driven, it is also an extension of BASIC programming in which commands and functions are combined with visual controls. VB was used as a tool for creating a GUI to manage library resources and operations in this regard [3]. According to [4], the authors examined the perception of staff and users, their satisfaction as well as their attitude toward open-source software. According to [5], the authors presented a paper on how the Library can be managed through the prospect of Unified Modeling Language (UML). Hence, UML was used to visualize a standard design of an LMS. The authors in [6] suggested that data transfer would be more efficient by employing cloud computing instead of wasting money on CDs tied along with books. According to [7], In their paper, they proffered a solution to some observed demerits of traditional library systems by using both struts and hibernate framework in popular multilayer tier architecture called Model View Controller (MVC) architecture to separate an application into logical components. Their approach was set to improve maintainability and reusability features in the system. According to [8], their proposal was specific to the flexible utilization of classes in Object Oriented Programming (OOP). Reusability of classes for similar conditions was their basic suggestion. The authors in [9] presented in their paper, a variety of open-source software such as journal management software, digital library software content, LMS, citation and journal management software, etc. According to the authors in [10], their paper is based on the comparison between the experiences and expectations of open-source software.

The authors in [11] proposed a paper that suggested the use of .Net Technology to design LMS. The high security offered by this approach is one of the best experiences ever enjoyed by users. The authors in [12] not only expose information about open-source software but also state its possible challenges.

The introduction of technology into the library system during the 1990s led to the actualization of the dreams of many researchers, students, and information and library practitioners. Through technology, the library's operations and procedures have improved immensely. The efficiency of service delivery to library clientele is also at its peak now.

According to [13], there exists an LMS also regarded as Integrated Library System (ILS) which serves as an enterprise resource planning for a library. It supports tracking library items, bill payments, and patrons, keeping a record of other possible payments made. The authors in [14] stated that for the correct implementation and use of LMS, knowledge is critical. According to [15], in their statement, they urged librarians and other staff of the library to possess knowledge of various types of LMS working principles and they should familiarize themselves with every module, feature, and operation of every LMS.

According to authors in [16], they observed that the effectiveness of LMS has been greatly reduced due to a lack of knowledge concerning the appropriate use of LMS facilities. According to authors in [17], library software is further classified into two different categories which are Proprietary Software (PS) and Open-source software (OSS), the difference between the two was also highlighted in this regard that OSS is free to purchase, it can easily be accessed, redistributed and modified by anyone with academic knowledge whereas PS has subscription fee and purchase fee associated with them. It is strictly modifiable by the owner of the software. This PS does not allow the general public to access its source codes. According to [18], PS amongst all LMS software remains the most popular one because it does not expose its users to risk, unlike the OSS which is associated with risk.

According to [19], LMS with web-driven client-server systems has continued to benefit users in general. Internet-enabled devices can easily be used to access library resources online since the current generation largely supports the emergence of the web.

2.1 SOME EXISTING IOT-BASED LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

2.1.1 Barcoding system library management system

A barcoding system involves the arrangement of a unique series of parallel bars or lines of varying width with underlying 12- digits which could be numbers and alphabets. They are used to enter data into the computer system when scanned by the barcode scanners.

In the library, the barcode is programmed to identify library assets such as books, CDs, Magazines, Journals, etc.

With the help of coding, details of every item with a barcode will reflect on the system when scanned. A Barcode system is usually used in the library to keep track of records of books borrowed, returned, or purchased in the library. Also, it is used to keep the inventory records of the library. Implementation and realization of this are based on the concept of the IoT because the wireless barcode scanner sends information about any scanned book or library asset to the library management software wirelessly to record what was captured.

A. How barcoding system Library management works

When a book or any library resource is scanned by the barcode scanner, the scanner captures the data and sends it directly to the library management software to display the information of the scanned book or library asset. This scanner most times communicates wirelessly with the software.

Figure 2.1: Example of a Barcode System [23].

Figure 2.2: Scanning of a Book Barcode by Using a Barcode Scanner [23].

Figure 2.3: Description of Barcode Patterns [23].

B. Advantages of barcoding system in library management

- (i) Improved inventory management
- (ii) Staff workload is highly reduced

(iii) It increases the library operation's efficiency and accuracy.

C. Disadvantages of barcoding system in the library management system

(i) The fact that every library item has to be scanned individually makes it labour-intensive.

(ii) It is not always a reliable method because if the barcode is damaged or ripped off, then such library material becomes impossible to scan to get its details.

(iii) It offers less security when compared to the RFID system.

(iv) Optical line of sight (LOS) is required.

2.1.2 QR CODE library management system

This works almost the same way as the barcoding system, the difference is not just in their pictorial pattern but also in the following aspects:

QR codes have the capability of holding more information than the Barcode system, for example, Information like the URL of the library can be included in it.

QR codes have the capability of still working perfectly even after about 30% of it is damaged, the QR code can still work unlike the barcoding systems that will stop working in that situation

The easy readability of QR codes usually makes it a better choice compared to the barcoding system because QR codes can be read from any angle and still give a perfect result unlike in a barcode system where the scanner has to be in line with the code.

2.1.3 RFID Library Management System

According to [25], RFID is also one of the technologies used extensively in our modern world basically for both tracking and monitoring physical objects. It is not only used in the library system, it is also used in several other sectors. RFID technology is used in the library system for three purposes:

- Theft detection and security system
- Inventory of library stock-taking
- Self-Check in/out

A. How RFID in library management works

The RFID system has three things: RFID tags, RFID readers, and radio waves.

In a library, for circulation and collection of library resources to be well managed, passive RFID tags of High-Frequency (HF) or Ultra High Frequencies (UHF) depending on the coverage area of concern. Passive RFID tags are used because they need no internal power source but get powered by electromagnetic energy that is being transmitted from the RFID reader, therefore for the RFID reader to give a sound, it must first generate an electromagnetic wave which will induce a voltage in the antenna of the RFID tag for an alert to be triggered. In a nutshell, it works on the principle of electromagnetic induction. UHF RFID tags have the capability of being read by the RFID reader at a range of up to 10-12 meters and a frequency range of about 860 – 960MHz.

The RFID tag is usually placed on the last cover of a book so that it can be recognized by the RFID reader. Placing it on the last cover of the book also helps to hide this RFID tag from library users. The use of RFID not only protects the library itself but also empowers users.

Figure 2.4: How RFID Reader Detects RFID Tags [23].

If a user wants **to borrow** a book, the RFID tag must be formally scanned to deactivate the card before it is issued for such use so that if the user tries to leave the library by following this procedure, the RFID reader will not raise the theft alarm but if the reader tries to leave the library without being formally issued the book, the RFID reader will raise alarm if such a user tries to leave the library. If a user **returns** a book then the tag will be reactivated.

B. Pictorial representation of operations of RFID in the library

Figure 2.5: Descriptive Image of RFID Tag [23].

Figure 2.6: How RFID Tag is placed on Last Page of a Book [23].

Figure 2.7: RFID System Support for Issuance of the Book to Users [23].

figure 2.8: RFID System Support for the Return of Book to the Library [23].

Figure 2.9: Library Stock-taking [23]

Figure 2.10: RFID Red-Light Security and Beeping for Detected Book Theft [23].

2.1.4 Smart Library with NFC Technology

This was introduced to the library system to advance the traditional library's operation. The need for technological aid to improve services rendered by existing library management brought about the potential use of Near Field Communication (NFC) to serve as an alternative to RFID Technology because

it is completely an extension of RFID. NFC is now used to enable computers, mobile phone tags, and other devices to communicate wirelessly across a small distance.

According to the authors in [20], they proposed a smart library which is generally regarded as S-library. The development enables library users to perform many library operations by simply using their smartphones. A mobile app is integrated with library management software communication by using an internet connection. Users first need to download and install it correctly on their mobile phones, then on mobile devices on which the apps can now be connected to the library management software and request library services.

As far as a smart library is concerned, the following functionalities are provided to users and these are: scanning and searching, borrowing and returning, and managing the library transactions.

As NFC card is used in libraries, and library assets such as books, CDs, Journals, Magazines, etc. each of these is attached to books. Common operations that are performed in the library using NFC technology involve **Scanning**: This is when the NFC tag is scanned by an NFC-enabled smartphone, and information/keywords such as title, author name, year, ISBN, etc. encoded in such library asset will be displayed. **Searching**: this is the process of searching for library assets by entering a related keyword into the search field in the app. **Borrowing and returning**: This is the functionality of the app that enables users to check in/out of any library asset of choice. This request will be sent to the LMS software to automatically update the database. **Library transaction management**: this takes care of any library activities that involve payments.

A. Advantages of NFC in library management

- Paperwork is highly reduced in this system.
- It is very efficient for transaction purposes.
- It empowers both users and librarians.

B. Disadvantages of NFC in library management

- High power consumption.
- It's not completely free from hackers i.e. it is not secure, since it supports payment/transaction.
- It is very expensive to implement.
- It covers only a short distance range usually 10-20cm.

- The data transfer rate is very low in NFC technology because its data transfer rate is just about 424Kbits/s.
- It is not compatible with all smartphones.

Figure 2.11: Book Scanning Process Based On NFC Technology.

Figure 2.12: App Interface Showing The Number Of Books Scanned That The User Can Buy, Borrow or Return.

Figure 2.13: Student's Library Activity Record as Generated by Scanned NFC Tags.

2.2 THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

2.2.1 Description of the proposed system

The proposed system is incorporated with an offline website that has database support for enabling book details storage. This will minimize the use of paper to record book details. The website will not only allow the librarians to store book records but will also enable librarians and users to search for books through this offline website and locate books through a signaling LED that comes on when a command is received from the NodeMCU microcontroller. The offline software will enable users to search for keywords such as ISBN, Author name, book title, etc. to get the location of the searched book instead of working around from shelf to shelf or checking many rows until a row in which the book is located is found. This system will also enable the library records to be kept in a computerized manner instead of using paper to keep a record of library books. **Therefore, this project is proposed to do three things:**

- (1) To handle storage of library book information in the database without the constant need for the internet.
- (2) To visually indicate the position of any book searched in the library through an LED Sensor.
- (3) To provide a solution to the problem of book misplacement in the library.

A. The advantages of the Proposed System are:

- 1) Reduction in data processing time.
- 2) Reduction in number of manpower needed for library operation in the aspect of record-taking
- 3) Faster access to book location.
- 4) Reduction in resource searching time.
- 5) Storage of library resource details into a database to reduce paperwork.

B. Disadvantages of the proposed system

As efficient and effective as it is, it does not allow the user to locate multiple books at once since the LED sensor only takes one command at a time, so the user will have to get the location for one request first before the next request can be processed.

Another factor is that there's a need to save the backup file of the updated SQL libraries in either cloud storage or other storage system such as Hard Disk Drives so that the updated version of the data stored on the database can be retrieved at any time even when the computer that housed the offline website file crashes. This is because our files rely solely on a local server, and a local server is considered a choice, in this case, eliminates incessant use of the internet for library operations, particularly while trying to locate the book.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

CHAPTER BRIEF

This chapter will focus on the hardware and software design of the project and some other aspects. A well-structured Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) such as requirement gathering, feasibility study, system analysis, software design, coding, testing, integration, implementation, operation, and maintenance will be employed in this project to ensure proper organization of the scope of the project so that a well-defined result would be obtained at the end of this project.

3.1 HARDWARE DESIGN AND COMPONENTS DESCRIPTION

3.1.1 5V Boost Step-Up Power Module & Lithium Battery Charging Protection Board.

(a) Power module

A power module or power electronic module provides the physical containment for several power components, usually power semiconductor devices. These power semiconductors (so-called dies) are typically soldered or sintered on a power electronic substrate that carries the power semiconductors and provides electrical and thermal contact and electrical insulation where needed.

(a) Charging module

As seen in the figure below, the charging module is built together with the power module. The smaller port enables direct charging of the lithium batteries using the constant current/constant voltage (CC/CV) charging method through the use of a 5V charger. These components are used together as a smart method because they offer the following advantages: intelligent temperature control with suitable over-temperature protection, support trickle mode, and zero voltage charging, charging, and discharging management.

Figure 3.1: Power Module and Charging Module [24].

3.1.2 NodeMCU board

NodeMCU is an open-source Lua-based firmware and development board specially targeted for IoT-based applications. It includes firmware that runs on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi SoC from Espressif Systems, and hardware that is based on the ESP-12 module. NodeMCU ESP8266 Specifications & Features are Microcontroller, Tensilica 32-bit RISC CPU Xtensa LX106, Operating Voltage: 3.3V, Input Voltage: 7-12V, Digital I/O Pins (DIO): 16, Analog Input Pins (ADC): 1, UARTs: 1, SPIs: 1, I2Cs: 1, Flash Memory: 4 MB, SRAM: 64 KB, Clock Speed: 80 MHz, USB-TTL based on CP2102 is included onboard, Enabling Plug and Play PCB Antenna, Small Sized module to fit smartly inside your IoT projects.

Figure 3.2: NodeMCU ESP-8266 V3 Board [26].

- **The Function of the NodeMCU Board in this Project**

NodeMCU Board is employed in this project to establish a connection between the software (offline website) and the hardware which incorporates LEDs (indicators to show books' location on the shelf). This NodeMCU Wi-Fi module must be well programmed and configured to act as a Hotspot in this project so that it can search for any device on which the software runs under the condition that the device has its Wi-Fi switched on and that it must always respond correctly to the signal received.

3.1.3 BC547 NPN Transistor

The BC547 is a widely used NPN transistor that can be used in any general-purpose application or as a substitute and replacement for many transistors. The BC547 can be used in a variety of electronic circuits, for example, switching the small load on very low input voltage and current. A transistor is a word coined from "transfer and resistance". This means that it is used for the transfer of resistance. BJTs generally are three-terminal devices used for the amplification of the current in electrical circuits and also as switching devices in an electronic circuit. Larger currents of the emitter and collector can be controlled by a very

small amount of the base current. When the input voltage is applied to the transistor, some voltage begins to flow from the base to the emitter, so that the collector current is regulated. For the NPN BJT, the voltage between the base and the emitter (V_{BE}) is positive for the base terminal and negative for the emitter.

Figure 3.3: BC547 Transistor [22].

- **BC547 Transistor Function in this Project**

BC547 Transistor is employed in this project as a switch which will help to switch ON/OFF LED as per command received from the NodeMCU board.

3.1.4 Switch

A switch is regarded as an electronic device or component that can switch an electric circuit and thereby interrupt conduction (flow of electrons in a circuit). The switch is also known as a binary device because the can be in an on or off state.

Figure 3.4: Switch [24].

- **The Function of the Switch in this Project**

Used for switching on and off the whole electronic hardware circuit.

3.1.5 3.7V Lithium-ion Battery

This is also known as a Li-ion battery, it is a type of battery in which light ion moves from the cathode (Negatively charged electrode) to the anode (positively charged electrode) during discharge and otherwise when charging. In a nutshell, a Li-ion battery is a type of rechargeable battery. It is widely used in portable consumer electronic devices.

Figure 3.5: Li-ion Battery [24].

- **The Function of the Li-ion Battery in this Project**

To power the circuit whenever required because it provides electromotive force (emf) which acts as the driving force to power the whole circuit.

3.1.6 Resistor

Resistors are passive components whose purpose is to resist or limit the flow of electricity in a circuit. The resistance of the resistor is measured in Ohms (Ω). They are also used as a potential divider to obtain a particular voltage value across a terminal. The resistors are of two types, namely:

- Fixed resistors and
- Variable resistors

The resistance of a material sample is described as the ratio of the voltage across the material to the current in it. The resistance value is depicted by the slope of the voltage and current graph. For a metallic material kept at a steady temperature, a straight-line graph shows that the material is Ohmic.

If ohms law is obeyed, resistance is calculated using the formula:

$$R = \frac{V}{I} \quad 2.1$$

Figure 3.6: Resistor [24].

- **The Function of the 10Kohm Resistor in this Project**

This is used to limit the excessive amount of current flowing through the base of the transistor, by doing this, the 5V output from the microcontroller is also dropped to 0.7v which is the operating voltage of the BC547 Transistor used.

3.1.7 8mm Super Bright LED

This is a semiconductor device that emits infrared or visible light when charged with an electric current. They are used in many applications such as remote controls and autofocus cameras. This LED is because it gives much brighter illumination since a high-intensity lighting solution is needed in this project. The super bright white coloured 8mm LED has a great viewing angle coupled with impressive light output. The aforementioned properties have made 8mm LED more useful in situations where 20 milliamperes cannot be used.

Figure 3.7: 8mm Super Bright LED [22].

- **The Function of LED in this Project**

Visible LEDs are used in the design and construction of this project as an indicator lamp to show which shelf has the book a user is searching for.

3.1.8 Liquid Crystal Display (LCD)

This is a flat-screened display that utilizes the light-modulating properties of liquid crystals to produce a visible image. They are super-thin display technologies that are used extensively in several applications such as a screen in smartphones, computers, televisions, and computers. They offer several advantages in the aspect of their features and these include high display quality, the capability of displaying a wider range of colours, higher resolution, and no electromagnetic radiation which could be hazardous to humans and the environment.

Figure 3.8: 16X2 LCD [24].

- **The Function of LCD in this Project**

LCD is used in this project as part of the hardware design to show information (such as IP address, and connection status) of any device trying to connect to a Wi-Fi-enabled microcontroller module (ESP-8266). By incorporating LCD into the design and construction concept of this project, we would be able to monitor the handshake or acknowledgment of data in transit between the sending and receiving devices. This LCD will help to display the IP of the device intending to connect to the microcontroller. This LCD shows important notifications such as its IP address.

3.1.9 Inter-Integrated Circuit (I2C)

This is also known as IIC, it is a multi-target/multi-controller, single-ended, synchronous, serial communication bus that has a communication protocol that allows one or more “Peripheral” usually digital integrated circuits (“chips”) to communicate with one controller. I2C was designed by NXP Semiconductors Company. Inter-Integrated Circuits are used in several areas such as in intelligent speakers where changing sound volume is necessary, it is also a useful power supply for system components and reading of diagnostic sensors and hardware monitors.

Figure 3.9: I2C (Inter-Integrated Circuit) [24].

- **The Function of I2C in this Project**

For connection of LCD to nodeMCU, this will require us to use more GPIO pins of the nodeMCU to connect to LCD successfully, but the fact that nodeMCU has a limited number of pins after we have

connected some of these pins to other components, hence, we need I2C to interface nodeMCU with the LCD by connecting the required pins from the LCD end to the pins of the I2C such that only two pins of the NodeMCU are now connected to the (SDA pin and SCL pin) of the I2C for connection to existing between the LCD and NodeMCU. It is through this connection that information to be displayed on the LCD screen is passed from the nodeMCU to the LCD. Other serial communication alternatives for interfacing NodeMCU with LCD include the use of SPI.

3.1.10 Plastic Casing

This is an enclosure that is used to protect electrical and electronic components and units in the box which also, in turn, prevents dust, dirt, oil, and water from entering the working area of the circuit. Other benefits of using plastic casing include the following:

- (i) It is extremely reliable.
- (ii) It makes the project last longer.
- (iii) It also enhances users' experience and interaction.
- (iv) It protects the internal elements in the box from external effects.

Figure 3.10: Plastic Casing [24].

3.2 ARCHITECTURE AND CIRCUIT DIAGRAM OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.2.1 The architecture of the proposed system

The operations of the architecture of the proposed system and the circuit diagram have been explained deeply on Pages [54-55] under the working principle of the proposed system.

Figure 3.11: Architecture of the Proposed System.

3.2.2 Circuit Diagram of the Proposed System

Figure 3.12: Circuit Diagram of the Proposed System.

3.3 OPERATIONAL REQUIREMENTS OF CIRCUIT COMPONENTS

3.3.1 Power Supply Unit

This is the circuit that supplies power to all other units of the design. This power supply unit is designed to be 5V DC tolerant through rectification of signal from a 220V AC mains supply and this constant 5V DC is tapped out from the power module and is fed into the NodeMCU board through the VIN pin to power it and the rest of the circuit and this further extends the supplied power to other units connected to it.

The parallel combination of batteries connected to this power module (a step-up booster) ensures increased current handling so that each of the cells can add to the overall ampere-hour (Ah) capacity of

the battery. From theory, we know well that connecting batteries in parallel does not only increase total current capacity but also decreases the total resistance.

- **Circuit Operational Requirement**

- **AC Supply Voltage:** The circuit can be powered by a 220V/50Hz power adapter which is converted to a direct current signal based on the voltage tolerance level (usually 5V DC) of the power module.
- **Batteries Option:** Batteries serving as a power bank in this design must be of the same model, equal voltage and capacity (Ah), and also batteries of a different age must not be mixed if the best result is expected. Two 3.7v batteries to be used must be connected in parallel. A 5v DC USB charger is preferred for charging.

Figure 3.13: Power Module structure and its connection to NodeMCU.

3.3.2 NodeMCU Board and ESP-8266 Wi-Fi Module

NodeMCU board is supplied with 5V DC with approximately 4000mAh through the pin marked as VIN so that a regulated 5V can power the whole circuit and still be obtained at the output level. As shown in the figure below, NodeMCU is connected to I2C (Inter-Integrated Circuit) and also connected to the external circuit switching ON/OFF the LEDs. The 5V DC supplied to this board at the input level remains constant at every point of the output.

- **Circuit Operational Requirements**
 - **ESP8266-01 Wi-Fi Module Operating Power:** voltage supplied into VIN must not be less than 5V (the operating voltage as far as the configuration of the cell with this project need is concerned) for this circuit to work satisfactorily with other connected external circuits. It must withstand the output amp-hour rating (approximately 4000mAh) fed into it from the power module since we have more components externally connected to it which in turn will draw more current from this board. Although the board itself consumes a low current of approximately (100mA).

Figure 3.14: NodeMCU Microcontroller and how it is connected to other components.

3.3.3 I2C PCF8546 for Interfacing NodeMCU ESP8266 with LCD

The **Serial Clock (SCL)** is the clock signal carrier and the **Serial Data (SDA)** is the line for the master and slave to send and receive data in transit. As shown in Figure 3.15, the SDA and SCL of the I2C are respectively connected to the **SD** and **SC** pins of the NodeMCU board and must be guided by a well-matching programming strategy so that the I2C and NodeMCU can communicate in the right way. Digital pins and analog pins of the **I2C** are then connected to those of the **LCD** as shown in the figure below so that required data can be successfully transmitted based on their matching protocols. This interfacing technique is used to suffice the need for more GPIO pins of NodeMCU to directly connect to LCD GPIO pins, hence, due to the insufficient number of pins on NodeMCU, I2C is employed to make provision for such.

- **Circuit Operational Requirement**

- **Input Voltage:** Voltage received by the I2C from the NodeMCU microcontroller remains 5V DC since the nodeMCU is configured to transmit at 5V in this project.
- **Operating Voltage:** The 5V supplied to the NodeMCU microcontroller board is maintained to be constant as output for other peripherals connected to it such as the I2C. Since the project design involves using VIN instead of the usual 3v or 3.3v pin.
- **Clock Frequency:** The maximum clock frequency of I2C is 100 kHz and the I2C clock frequency must be higher than the lowest frequency of the slave device.
- **Input Current:** it must draw as much current as possible from the NodeMCU to make provisions for the current needed by the LCD since the LCD itself consumes a minimum current of approximately 100mA.

Figure 3.15: How I2C PCF8546 Interfaces NodeMCU ESP8266 with LCD.

3.3.4 External Circuit LED Sensors

As discussed earlier, LEDs attached to shelves will blink to indicate the location of the book of interest on the shelf.

As shown in Figure 3.16, the NodeMCU board will supply 5V output to this external circuit, so that any GPIO receiving signal as that of the command sent from the software will switch ON the LED mapped

to such command through the BC547 transistor attached to such GPIO pin since transistor configuration, in this case, is to act as a switch. Each BC547 NPN transistor has a 10kΩ resistor attached to it so that this resistor can limit the current flow in the LED to around 100mA or slightly above.

- **Circuit Operational Requirements**

- **Input voltage (V_{IN}):** This is the NodeMCU board output voltage serving as the input voltage for the external circuit through which the NodeMCU board communicates with this external circuit incorporating the LEDs and transistors. Since the microcontroller operates on a 5V supply, it transmits at the same voltage.
- **Transistor’s Operational Voltage:** For the transistor to work, the supply voltage from the NodeMCU board is dropped from 5V to 0.7V at 430μA based on the 10kΩ base resistor used. This is necessary because if the base current in I_B is not limited, excessive base current can cause the transistor to be damaged.

Figure 3.16: Interconnection of Nodemcu Microcontroller with an External Circuit.

CALCULATIONS

By formula,

$$I_E = I_C + I_B \tag{3.1}$$

Where I_B=Base current, I_C=Collector current, I_E=Emitter current

But I_C must be much larger than I_B so that approximately $I_E = I_C$

According to [21], From BC547 Transistor datasheet, maximum collector current $I_C = 100\text{mA}$, maximum base current $I_B = 5\text{mA}$, maximum DC Current gain (h_{FE}) = 800

Then we can say that from our circuit configuration, the base current can be calculated in terms of voltage and resistance values of other components.

$$I_B = \frac{V_{BB} - V_{BE}}{R_B} \quad 3.2$$

Also, the base current I_B flows only when the V_{BE} which is the voltage across the base-emitter junction is 0.7v or more, since V_{IN} is known to be 5V, $V_{IN} = V_{BB}$, we can then obtain the value of I_B

$$I_B = \frac{5V - 0.7V}{1000\Omega}$$
$$I_B = 430\mu A.$$

If we substitute this into the current equation of the transistor then we will realize that $I_E = I_C$ (**Approximately**) since I_B is very small in this case.

$$I_E = 100\text{mA} + 430\mu A$$
$$I_E \approx 100\text{mA}$$

Since the transistor is chosen to act as a switch in this project, the power developed (usually in the form of heat) inside the transistor will be very small.

Power (P) developed in the transistor is given as

$$P = I_C \times V_{CE} \quad 3.3$$

This power varies under the following circuit conditions:

When the circuit is OFF: Power is zero because I_C is also equal to zero.

When the circuit is ON: Power is very small since V_{CE} is almost equal to zero.

3.3.5 8mm LED Operation Requirement

This super bright white LED is used as the major indicator in this project. It shows the actual location of a book on the shelf when such a book is searched for. It is very bright that the location of the book can easily be found when this LED is switched ON.

- **Input Voltage:** An approximate 5v supplied from the output pin of the nodeMCU board remains the input for the LED to work perfectly.

According to [22], the datasheet of 8mm LED specification is given as shown in the figure below.

LED Model	Optical Qualities	Electrical Characteristics
White Super Bright 	Intensity: 16,000 mcd	Voltage: 3.4v-3.7v
WC801-01	Colour Freq: 6,000K-6,500K	Typical 3.6v
	Viewing Angle: 140°	Current: 150mA
	Lens: Water Clear	Peak Pulse: 200mA

Figure 3.17: Features of 8mm Super Bright LED [22].

Input Current: it can withstand a current of up to 150mA as shown in the datasheet in Figure 3.17. This is very valid because the collector current which was said to be 100mA for the BC547 transistor is still the current flowing through the LED and this is still close to the current given in the ratings supported by the 8mm LED as shown in the datasheet.

3.4 SOFTWARE DESIGN

The software design phase of this project is categorized into two:

- (1) Programming of the NodeMCU ESP8266 V3 Microcontroller module by using C++ programming Language).
- (2) Building the software (Offline website) by using some set of tools such as (PHP Programming language, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, XAMPP Server, and SQL).

3.4.1 Programming of the NodeMCU ESP8266 V3 Microcontroller Module

Step 1: This first step is to connect the NodeMCU to the computer system by using a micro USB cable (USB Cable that supports power supply and data transmission). Once the built-in LED of the NodeMCU blinks, it means that it is powered on and connected to the computer for data transmission to begin.

Step 2: Compactible driver for this NodeMCU is downloaded online, extracted, and installed on the Computer system. The driver is available at <https://www.siliconlabs.com>.

Step 3: Next is to install Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE), start it, and open the preferences window.

Step 4: from the window, use the Arduino tools hyperlink to open the board manager.

Step 5: Then select and install the ESP8266 platform from the board menu.

Step 6: Necessary settings such as network credentials, coding, and configuration of the NodeMCU GPIO Pins as well as necessary matching of GPIO Pins with the software command will then be performed.

Step 7: Upload codes into the NodeMCU board using a C++ programming language.

Step 8: Remove the micro USB cable from the system and the NodeMCU Board end.

3.4.2 Building the software (Offline website)

- **Software tools used**

The software design phase is broken down into two categories, namely:

- Frontend and Backend Tools

- **FRONTEND DEVELOPMENT TOOLS**
 - **HyperText Markup Language (HTML)**

This is a well-known computer language that is extremely useful when it comes to the creation of web pages and displaying information in a web browser. As the name implies, **Hypertext** is simply text that can be used to reference other pieces of text whereas the **Markup Language** simply describes the style and structure of a document to a web browser. HTML has several elements. Some of these elements do have opening and closing tags while some do not have closing tags but have opening tags. HTML tags are unique in that they are not displayed on the browser since they only specify the format of the document.

- **Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)**

Is a style sheet language used for formatting a document and describing the presentation documents written in a markup language such as HTML, CSS together with HTML, and JavaScript have been regarded as the cornerstone technology of the World Wide Web? CSS is also applied in an XML document, including plain XML, SVG, and XUL. CSS enables two or more pages to share formatting and reduces complexity and repetition in the structural content. CSS can also allow the same markup page to be presented in different styles for different rendering methods. CSS allows software designers to give a website beauty of all kinds such as applying fonts, and colors, and laying out contents in columns and rows.

- **JavaScript**

JavaScript (JS) is a dynamic computer programming language that adapts to European Computer Manufacturers Association (ECMA) specifications. It is useful for updating content, animating images, controlling multimedia, and communicating asynchronously and alters the document content that is displayed. JavaScript is a prototype-based scripting language with dynamic typing and has first-class functions. It adds interactivity to websites and is very useful for creating network-centric applications. It is a very popular client-side scripting language.

- **Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP)**

PHP is regarded as a general-purpose programming scripting language. It is extremely useful for web development projects due to its fastness, and flexibility, and it is pragmatic. It has been used extensively

to power most blogs and popular websites because it serves as a powerful tool for creating dynamic and interactive web pages. It is a language that is interpreted by a web server with a PHP processor module, which in turn generates the desired web pages. PHP works hand in hand with HTML and hence, they are embedded together to form a whole source document rather than processing data by calling an external file. It can be used as a standalone graphical application. PHP is free and efficient and it can be deployed on almost all web servers and also as an independent shell on almost all operating systems and platforms. PHP has been seen as an efficient alternative to competitors such as Microsoft's ASP.

- **BACKEND DEVELOPMENT TOOLS**

- **My Structured Query Language (MySQL)**

This is considered the second most widely used open-source Relational Database Management System (RDBMS) in the world. MySQL is very popular in that it is used extensively for both small and large applications. It is very useful for managing, accessing, and manipulating records in the database. It is easy to use, fast, and scalable database management system when compared with Oracle database and Microsoft SQL Server. It is also commonly used in conjunction with PHP Scripts. It will be of great importance in this project most especially in the areas of table creation and data management.

- **XAMPP SERVER**

Cross-platform, Apache, MySQL, PHP, and Perl (XAMPP) allow developers to build an offline website on a local server on a computer system before it is eventually released to the main server. XAMPP software package contains Apache distributions for Apache Server, MySQL, PHP, and Perl) which creates a local web server for testing and deployment purposes.

XAMPP is not just a server but a bundle of web-server products. It provides the administrator with the following features:

Apache (this runs codes written in PHP and also responds to Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) requests).

MySQL (the database that stores data).

File Transfer Protocol (FTP): This is the tool that is used to upload and download files from your server.

XAMPP is employed in this project as a local server on which this IoT-based library management system software will run.

3.5 USER REQUIREMENT

User requirements will be classified into two basic categories in this project

- Functional requirement
- Non-functional requirement

3.5.1 Functional Requirement

- The system must be able to allow Admin to register a new user account.
- The system must allow only users with valid login IDs and passwords to access it.
- The system must be able to perform authorization and authentication processes based on the user level.
- The system must be able to log out of users' accounts after they have finished using the system.
- The system must be able to allow the administrators to change user passwords or retrieve their login credentials when lost.
- The system must be able to verify information completely.
- The system must be able to enter correct information about the book into the database.
- The system must be able to search the database for the book based on selected keywords (ISBN, Book Title, and Author Name).
- Through the use of the correct keyword by the user, the system must be able to filter books based on the user's request.
- A list view of books that match the user request must pop up and the user must be able to click on any.
- The system must be able to send commands to the microcontroller that controls the LED sensors anytime the user clicks on the Locate button.

3.5.2 Non-Functional Requirements

- The system must be able to respond accurately to the user's request
- The system must be able to process information very fast.
- The system must be user-friendly and always give error messages when necessary.

3.6 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The minimum requirements that must be met by the computer system running the software before it can give the desired results are shown in the table below.

Table 3.1: System Requirements of This Project.

1	Hard Disk Capacity	Minimum of 4-6GB to include database usage for future
2	RAM Capacity	The system running the software must have RAM of at least 2GB
3	Screen resolution	1024 x 768
4	Processor	Intel Pentium 233GHz or better performance
5	Operating System	Window 10 or higher version that supports hotspot features
6	Database	MySQL
7	Local server	XAMPP Server

ENTITY RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM OF THE SYSTEM

Figure 3.18: Entity Relationship Diagram

3.7 E-R DIAGRAM

An entity-relationship diagram used in this chapter is used to show the relationship that exists among entity sets. Geometric shapes are applied to give the E-R diagram the best look. The rectangular shape is used to represent the **Entity**, the Ellipse shape is used to represent the **Attribute** of each entity, the Diamond shape is used to represent the **Relationship** among entities while lines are used to link attributes with an entity and also used to link entity with the relationship. These entities and their attributes will be used to formulate our database tables. So, Figure 3.18 is the complete logical structure of the database of this project.

3.8 USER /ADMIN FLOWCHART OF HOW TO GET BOOK LOCATION

Figure 3.19: Flowchart of User Interaction with the Software to Get a Book Location.

From the flowchart shown in Figure 3.19, a user must enter keywords that accurately describe a book before the information about the book can be fetched from the database. If information about the book is found, then the user can click on the "locate" button to get the location of the book through the shelf that has the blinking LED now.

3.9 THE HARDWARE-SOFTWARE INTERACTION FLOWCHART

Figure 3.20: The Hardware-Software Interaction Flowchart.

Figure 3.20 represents how the software and the hardware part of this project interact from the initial stage to the final stage. For successful connection and communication to exist between the hardware and the software, several steps must be taken into consideration and the steps involved are logically described in Figure 3.20.

3.10 WORKING PRINCIPLE OF THE HARDWARE-SOFTWARE SYSTEM

The NodeMCU board acts as the fundamental part of this design. When the nodeMCU is powered by the power module, this NodeMCU will in turn supply signals to other peripherals (such as I2C and 16x2 LCD) and external circuits (circuits containing the LED and others that are connected to it. This NodeMCU ESP-8266 Wi-Fi module on the microcontroller board is programmed in such a way that it acts as a Hotspot that remains switched for the available Wi-Fi-enabled devices on which the designed software (offline website) runs under the condition that the pre-programmed NodeMCU Network Name and Password must match with the network credentials of the computing device trying to connect to it wirelessly. This ESP-8266 Wi-Fi module responds to signals from the external software (offline website) that resides on a computer system. The Microcontroller module now sends the received signals through its output pin to an external circuit linking transistors and LEDs together so that the transistor acting as a switch can turn ON the LED attached to the shelf row in which the book of interest is located immediately, depending on which LED matches with the signal command. Also, I2C is used to interface the NodeMCU with 16x2 LCD to display the unique IP address of this Microcontroller, this NodeMCU IP address is then copied and updated in the IP request field on the offline website so that the host computer can establish a continuous connection with the microcontroller. Commands will then be sent from the microcontroller to available transistors acting as switches to switch on the LED that matches the command sent from the website by the user, then the **LED** with the required response will blink five times.

- (a) When the device is found and the connection is established, the LCD outputs the IP **“192.168.4.1”**
- (b) Once the connection is made, the ESP-8266 Wi-Fi module will assign the next IP address **(192.168.4.2)** to the host computer on which the software file and the XAMPP are located. This new IP (192.168.4.2) can then be pinged (visited) by other devices such as a smartphone or computer system that which is ready to use the library web files available on the host computer. With this technique, successfully connected computers or smartphones to the software facilities will now have the capability to search and locate books by communicating with the microcontroller. When a command such as **“locate”** is sent from the software, then the LED attached to the book location will blink immediately.

4.0 IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 HARDWARE CONSTRUCTION AND TESTING

4.1.1 Hardware Construction

This section fully describes the processes followed in building the hardware part of the project. It involves how the power unit is connected to the NodeMCU Microcontroller and other sub-units, and how the microcontroller is connected to other sub-units such as LCD, I2C, transistors, resistors, and LED. The entire construction process was carried out using different techniques to ensure that the desired result was obtained. The circuit configuration was first carried out on a breadboard to ensure that the circuit design prepared on paper works perfectly well before the final construction can be done on the Vero board for the actual realization of the project goals. After successfully constructing the hardware circuit, it was then enclosed in a plastic casing to protect it from dust and moisture that can affect its internal components. Processes undergone are:

- (1) Circuit analysis and construction using a breadboard to test the workability of components to use.
- (2) Using Vero-board to realize the final construction by identifying points to solder components.
- (3) Soldering of components to the board.
- (4) Testing of continuity, voltage, current, and resistance across components for requirements.
- (5) Observing the firmness of interconnected components.
- (6) Enclosing the hardware into a plastic casing.
- (7) Building of shelf and fixing the hardware casing to the shelf.

Figure 4.1: Picture collections of the step-by-step construction of the hardware.

Figure 4.2: Picture Collections of Step-By-Step Construction of the Hardware.

4.1.2 Hardware Testing and Results

All components used are developed in such a way that their interconnection determines the effectiveness, correctness, efficiency, reliability, and robustness of the proposed system. Unit testing was carried out on individual components by using a multimeter to verify and ensure all components were at the required minimum functional level.

- (i) **Voltage, Current, Resistance, and Power Test:** A digital multimeter was essentially used in this project to determine the level of some component parameters such as continuity, voltage, frequency, current, temperature, and resistance. The output voltage of the power module, output voltage and current at NodeMCU input and output pins, input and output voltage, current and resistance across other components such as (transistor, resistor, LED, etc).
- (ii) **Hardware-Software Wi-Fi Range:** The maximum distance between the hardware and the device on which the software (offline website) runs should not be more than 30 - 40m.
- (iii) **Response Time:** The LED sensors respond to a user command in a matter of less than 1 second.
- (iv) **Number of devices that can connect to the network:** The maximum number of devices that can ping the host computer's offline website files cannot exceed 10. To visit the host computer, other devices (computer or smartphone) must first connect to the e-library microcontroller hardware hotspot by using this credential.

SSID to connect to: elibrary

Password/security key: *****

Then enter into their browser the address shown below.

<https://www.192.168.4.2/elibrary>

Figure 4.3: Picture of the bookshelf with LED Attached to it to indicate book location

Complete Hardware Testing and Result (with blinking LED)

Figure 4.3: Search and Locate Row 1 Resource. Figure 4.4: Search and Locate Row 2 Resource.

Figure 4.5: Search and Locate Row 3 Resource. Figure 4.6: Search and Locate Row 4 Resource.

4.2 SOFTWARE TESTING

Responsiveness of every part of the software was examined in this section through unit testing, how fast the software can respond to user input commands and get the request forwarded to the hardware to output desired results. Synchronization between the user device and the software was fully tested to ensure that the system possesses the expected latency. Also, an integration test was carried out to ensure that independent modules are then integrated to verify the functionality of the interface of each component to point out defects associated with them and the behavior or responsiveness of each component interacting together.

4.2.1 Administrator Dashboard Module

This page enables the library admin to update the website IP field with the required IP of the microcontroller. On this Admin dashboard, the admin can add users, manage users, add books, and manage books. This page shows the list of registered books, admin, and users.

Figure 4.7: Administrator Dashboard.

4.2.2 Add Book Module

This module enables the admin to add new books to the database of the offline websites. These books will be made available to users to locate through their accounts.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `www.localhost/vlibrary/admin/add-book.php`. The page header includes the logo for 'Online Library Management System' and a 'LOG ME OUT' button. A navigation menu contains 'DASHBOARD', 'BOOKS', 'USERS', 'ADMINS', and 'CHANGE PASSWORD'. The main heading is 'ADD BOOK'. The form is titled 'Book Info' and includes the following fields:

- ISBN Number***: A text input field with a note below it: 'An ISBN is an International Standard Book Number ISBN Must be unique'.
- Book Name***: A text input field.
- Author Name***: A text input field with a note below it: 'Name of Author'.
- Quantity***: A text input field.
- Edition***: A text input field with a note below it: 'Edition'.
- Pages***: A text input field with a note below it: 'Pages'.
- Publisher***: A text input field with a note below it: 'Publisher'.
- Price***: A text input field.
- Location***: A dropdown menu with the text 'Select Location'.

A blue 'Add Book' button is located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 4.8: Page to Add a Book to the Library Management System Database.

4.2.3 Manage Books Module

This enables the library administrator to manage existing book information. Through this feature, the administrator can modify book information by using (update/edit), and the administrator can also delete existing book information.

Figure 4.9: Page for Admin to Manage Books.

4.2.4 User Signup Module

This module enables the admin to create an account for users. In this project, only one account is created for general use by all users. This user email and password created by the admin will be posted in the library so that users can always make use of it in their comfort in the library to access the offline website.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying "www.localhost/eilibrary/admin/add-users.php". The page title is "Online Library Management System" with a book icon. A "LOG ME OUT" button is visible in the top right. A navigation menu includes "DASHBOARD", "BOOKS", "USERS", "ADMINS", and "CHANGE PASSWORD". The main content area is titled "USER SIGNUP" and contains a "SIGNUP FORM" with the following fields: "Enter Full Name", "Mobile Number:", "Enter Email", "Enter Password", "Enter Password", and "Confirm Password". A "Register Now" button is located at the bottom of the form.

Figure 4.10: Page for User Registration.

4.2.5 User Login Module

This module gives users access to log in and make use of the website, they can search and locate their book of choice when needed.

Figure 4.11: Page for User Login.

4.2.6 User Dashboard Module

This is where the user proceeds upon logging into his/her account. Users can use the reserved search field to search for keywords related to a book and then click on the “locate” button to get the location of the book on the shelf in a matter of seconds.

Online Library Management System

LOG ME OUT

DASHBOARD ACCOUNT

ADEKOLA OLUWASEUN DASHBOARD

4

Available Book

Books Listing

10 records per page Search:

#	ISBN No	Book Title	Author Name	Quantity	Last UpDated	Edition	Pages	Publisher	Action
1	9780367643782	Bird Engineering Mathematics	John Bird	500	2022-06-05 14:12:19	second	758	Routledge	Locate
2	9781137031228	ENGINEERING MATHEMATICS	KA STROUD	50	2022-06-05 14:08:48	Seventh	1184	Macmillan International Higher	Locate
3	978036762225	ELECTRICAL CIRCUIT THEORY AND TECHNOLOGY	JOHN BIRD	55	2022-06-05 14:28:09	Seventh	930	Routledge	Locate
4	9788121924900	A TEXTBOOK OF ELECTRICAL TECHNOLOGY	BL THERAJA	56	2022-06-05 14:41:20	reprint	2016	Chand	Locate

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

[Previous](#)
1
[Next](#)

Figure 4.12: User Dashboard.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

The exponential growth of connected devices has enabled IoT to give a more reliable solution to more organizational challenges. IoT has been a solver of many challenges, especially when an organization is challenged with monitoring, securing, and managing a large number of data and connections from different devices. The term IoT is adopted in this project because of the need to get some devices connected to a network to automate some tasks. The proposed project also avoids the use of the internet to access the website, and this is a great cost saver because the cost of subscribing to use the internet can be very high and could go beyond the budget separated for it if care is not taken. Hence, the offline mode of working is one of the advantages of this project.

This IoT-based library management system enables library users to search and locate books in the library more quickly in a matter of seconds because the microcontroller (NodeMCU) receives commands from the computer software and then activates the sensor attached to the shelf to show the row in which the book of interest is located. Its accessibility is not limited to the use of a computer system only, smartphone users can also connect to the host computer to access the offline software facilities under the condition that the system is not too overwhelmed. Library admin may provide about 9 other laptops which will all be connected to the host computer that houses the localhost server so that they can all have shared access to the network and the offline website files, and through this, users can use different laptops to locate books on the shelf, this will reduce the time spent by users on roaming around from shelf to shelf in search of books. Through this project, the low communication latency and a high degree of responsiveness from connected devices will not only enhance the library management system activities digitally but also enable IoT solutions to continue to scale globally in other projects.

This project can be used by libraries with a small and large number of books because it offers more effective handling and maintenance features, and these features make the project function in a more sophisticated way than the manual library management system.

One of the basic advantages of this project to me personally lies in the fact that I gained more practical knowledge in the field of electronics and programming world. The project I felt I could not accomplish

from the onset has now been finally achieved due to my consistent efforts and determination to take up any challenge that I stumble upon. Learning PHP programming language and other programming fundamentals to achieve the results of my project aim was difficult for me in the beginning but after some months of being consistent with learning it, it has exposed me to how to use PHP programming language well to develop more projects in real life.

The proposed system has been tested and observed to be very efficient in terms of parameters like technology use, low power consumption, less amount of time to perform the tasks needed by users, and its power unit can last for nearly 12 hours when fully charged and used continuously, and the overall system also reduces librarian's workload. The proposed project follows a framework that provides information about the misplaced book.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Library administrators should give prior guidelines that support the “how to use it” of the deployed system so that the system can be used more conveniently. Training should be periodically given to librarians too on how the system works and how to use it innovatively. No ICT-based facility can work perfectly without an adequate power supply, hence, a power supply is also important in the library for charging and recharging the power module of the proposed system, although the system has a power module with a backup of roughly 12 hours. This system has solved the problems of information management systems in the library as well as resource searching and locating time with no internet cost. Also, for future research purposes, possible areas in which this project can further be enhanced are stated below.

IoT server-side systems, gateways, and other communicating devices connected over a network should consider issues like authorization, secure authentication, encryption, and protection from denial of service. This is highly important in IoT projects that are intended to be configured to work online.

A well-secured standard online server is preferable as data would be stored in a reliable database. Although the proposed system uses a local server and anytime the library database is updated, its copy should also be exported and saved to external storage like HDD or cloud so that a backup file can be reused whenever the laptop that houses the local server and the project folder encounter problems.

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APPENDIX

All codes available at:

<https://www.github.com/SafersTechnologies/elibrary>